

Research protocol

Microbiology in pleural effusions in the intensive care unit: A retrospective cohort study

Research group

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Background

Pleural effusions are prevalent in intensive care unit (ICU) patients, ranging from 37% to 80% when assessed ultrasonographically.¹⁻⁴ A recent observational study from Aalborg University Hospital found that 31% (25/81) of patients had or developed ultrasonographically significant pleural effusion during ICU admission, of which 40% received thoracentesis.⁵ When thoracentesis is conducted, a pleural fluid culture is usually performed. Thoracentesis in the ICU with culturing is specifically recommended diagnostically in the cases of parapneumonic pleural effusions, unresolved infection especially with unclear focus, or persistent effusions.^{6,7} Indications for therapeutic drainage however, remain unresolved.⁶⁻¹⁰ The diagnosis of unsuspected pleural infection has been proposed as an argument for routine thoracentesis in all patients with pleural effusion in the ICU.⁸ Despite the importance of diagnosing pleural infection in relation to thoracentesis in ICU patients, the prevalence of positive cultures from pleural fluid from patients admitted to the ICU has not been characterized in a large ICU population, specifically not in relation to indications for thoracentesis.

Aims and hypotheses

We aim to quantify the prevalence of positive cultures from pleural fluid in patients admitted to the ICU according to the indication for thoracentesis and presence of ipsilateral pneumonia. We will further correlate microbiological findings of the pleural fluid to other microbiologic test results including blood cultures and cultures of airway secretions, and to 90-day mortality.

We hypothesize that positive cultures from primary pleural fluid samples from adult ICU patients are rare (<10%). That diagnostic thoracentesis is associated with a higher incidence of positive cultures than therapeutic thoracentesis. And that parapneumonic effusions are associated with a higher incidence of positive cultures than non-parapneumonic effusions. Secondary, we hypothesize that a positive culture from pleural fluid is associated with a higher 90-day all-cause mortality than a negative culture in adult ICU patients where thoracentesis with pleural fluid sampling for culturing is conducted.

Methods

This is a retrospective regional observational cohort study.

Population and settings

All adult patients (aged 18 years or above) who were admitted to one of the eight ICUs in the North Denmark Region and had culturing of pleural fluid conducted during ICU stay in a 10-year period

from March 1, 2013 to February 28, 2023 will be included. All conducted cultures of pleural fluid within the inclusion period for each patient will be included.

Data sources

ICU patients with pleural fluid culture conducted in the inclusion period will be identified in the regional microbiological laboratory information system (LIS), and data of culture results, time of sampling and antibiotic treatment prior to sampling, and results from blood and airway secretion cultures performed within 30 days prior to primary pleural fluid sampling and during ICU admission will be obtained. Time of ICU admission and discharge, comorbidities (chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, chronic kidney failure, ischemic heart disease or chronic heart failure, diabetes, and active cancer at hospital admission), hospital admission diagnosis including codes for surgery performed prior to pleural fluid sampling, and latest blood sample results (plasma C-reactive protein, plasma procalcitonin and white blood cell count) prior to the primary pleural fluid sampling will be assessed using codes in the administrative databases and extracts from biochemical databases, obtained through the business intelligence (BI) unit in the North Denmark Region. The number of patients who received thoracentesis in the ICU in the inclusion period with or without pleural fluid for culturing will be obtained from the BI unit as well. Data on indication for thoracentesis, date of procedure, presence of pneumonia, use of life-support in the ICU prior to pleural fluid sampling, and 90-day mortality from time of pleural fluid sampling will be obtained through patient medical journal review.

Patient identification and linkage between the LIS and electronic patient medical journal at the individual level will be ensured through the national Danish unique personal registration number and additionally, age as well as legal gender will be readily available from this.¹¹

Exposures

The patients will be divided into two main exposure groups depending on the indication for thoracentesis being (1) diagnostic or (2) therapeutic. A diagnostic thoracentesis will be defined as any mentioning of suspected or possible risk of pleural infection or empyema during hospital admission prior to thoracentesis in the reference note for drainage, in radiological descriptions prior to drainage, or in the medical journal. All other thoracenteses will be considered therapeutic. A secondary exposure will be the presence of parapneumonic effusion or not. A parapneumonic effusion will be defined from ipsilateral pneumonic infiltrate on radiologic imaging prior to pleural fluid sampling in combination with increased infectious parameters (white blood cell counts, c-reactive protein, or pro-calcitonin), fever (temperature $\geq 38^{\circ}$ C) or airway secretion culture results, or specification of ipsilateral pneumonia in the medical journal during hospital admission prior to pleural fluid sampling.

Potential confounders

Antibiotic therapy received prior to pleural fluid sampling will be categorized according to the World Health Organization Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC)¹² antimicrobial classes (from lowest to highest spectrum, if antibiotics from several groups have been received, the group with the highest spectrum will be used in the analysis): (1) no antibiotics received, (2) beta-lactamase sensitive penicillins (J01CE), (3) macrolides, lincosamides and streptogramins (J01F), (4) cephalosporins (J01DB-E), aminoglycoside antibacterials (J01GB), imidazole derivatives (J01XD), triazole and tetrazole derivatives (J02AC), amphotericin B (J02AA01), or other antimycotics for systemic use (J02AX) (e.g. caspofungin and anidulafungin), (5) combinations of penicillins, incl. beta-lactamase inhibitors (J01CR) (e.g., piperacillin/tazobactam and amoxicillin/clavulanic acid), or combinations of sulfonamides and trimethoprim, incl. derivatives (J01EE), (6) tetracyclines (JH01AA), fluoroquinolones (J01MA) or glycopeptide antibacterials (J01XA), and (7) carbapenems (J01DH). Conducted related cultures from 30 days prior to primary pleural fluid sampling will be divided in two variables according to culture type (airway secretion or blood), each dichotomized according to result: (1) positive culture in any sample of one or more bacterial or fungal species considered of pathological significance, and (2) negative or non-pathologically significant culture result, or not conducted (missing). In blood, all cultured microorganisms will be considered of pathological significance. In airway secretions, cultures of bacteria considered as part of the normal oropharyngeal flora, as evaluated by our microbiologists, will be considered contamination and therefore pathologically non-significant. Positive polymerase chain reaction results for atypical bacteria, e.g., *Legionella*

pneumophila, *Mycoplasma pneumoniae*, and *Chlamydia psittaci* or *pneumoniae*, conducted on airway secretions will be considered equal to a positive culture. In the mortality analysis, additional potential confounders will include age, comorbidities (dichotomized in five groups: (1) chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, (2) chronic kidney failure, (3) ischemic heart disease or chronic heart failure, (4) diabetes, and (5) active cancer), gender, and life-support received during ICU admission prior to pleural fluid sampling according to organ support therapies received categorized in three dichotomous variables as ‘any use of’: (1) invasive mechanical ventilation defined as mechanical positive pressure ventilation through an endotracheal tube; (2) cardiovascular support, defined as treatment with continuously infused inotropic agents or vasopressors; and (3) renal replacement therapy of any type (continuous or intermittent).

Outcomes

The primary outcome will be a positive pleural fluid culture of any bacteria or fungi considered of pathological significance e.g., *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Streptococcus anginosus*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and anaerobes, whereas coagulase-negative Staphylococci, Enterococci, and *Corynebacterium* species, will be considered contaminants.¹³

Secondary outcome will be all-cause mortality within 90 days from the primary pleural fluid sampling, which will be evaluated in relation to the primary outcome.

Blinding

The researchers will strictly assess patients’ individual indications for thoracentesis and presence of parapneumonic effusion prior to assessing results of the pleural fluid culture and will therefore be blinded to the primary outcome when evaluating the exposures.

Statistics

Baseline characteristics prior to pleural fluid sampling will be reported for the entire cohort, as well as according to positive pleural culture or not. Categorical variables will be reported using frequencies and percentages. Continuous variables will be reported as medians with the 25th and 75th percentiles or means \pm standard deviations (SD) as appropriate.

Only the first pleural fluid culture within the inclusion period for each patient will be included in the statistical analyses unless specified otherwise.

In the primary analysis, we will assess the primary outcome in the two main exposure groups (diagnostic and therapeutic thoracentesis) using a generalized linear model with a log-link, Poisson distribution and a robust variance estimation (VCE(robust)),¹⁴ adjusted for antibiotics (dichotomous – yes/no), and related cultures (blood and airway secretions), comparing the risk ratio (RR) with 95% confidence interval (CI), with therapeutic thoracentesis as the reference. Comparisons of the secondary exposure groups (parapneumonic effusion or not) will be analyzed similarly in a secondary analysis.

To investigate different effects in subgroups (effect measure modification), indications for thoracentesis (diagnostic or therapeutic), will be tested for interactions with presence of parapneumonic effusion, and related cultures (blood and airway secretions), and if significant interactions are found, a supplemental analysis stratified by these factors will be presented.

Supplementally, we will report the sensitivity and specificity with 95% CIs for predicting a positive pleural fluid culture of diagnostic thoracentesis and parapneumonic effusion, respectively.

A secondary analysis will be conducted investigating all-cause mortality within 90 days, compared according to the primary outcome between patients with positive pleural fluid culture, and patients without this, using a generalized linear model with a log-link, Poisson distribution and VCE(robust),¹⁴ adjusted for antibiotics (categorical, prioritized), related cultures (blood and airway secretions), age (in years), comorbidities, gender, and life-support in the ICU. Significance of the differences in 90-day mortality between patients with and without positive pleural fluid culture will be assessed based on the RR with 95% CI from this regression analysis with patients without positive pleural fluid culture as the reference. Effect measure modification on 90-day mortality will also be evaluated according to the primary outcome between patients with positive pleural fluid culture, and patients without this, with tests for interactions of indication for thoracentesis (diagnostic or therapeutic), presence of parapneumonic effusion, and related cultures (blood and airway secretions),

and if significant interactions are found, a supplemental analysis stratified by these factors will be presented. In all tests for interactions, a p-value below 0.05 will be considered statistically significant. In all analyses the unadjusted RRs with 95% CIs will be supplementally reported as well. Results will be illustrated with Forrest plots as suitable, and survival in 90 days from pleural fluid sampling with Kaplan-Meier plots in patients with and patients without positive pleural fluid culture, respectively. If less than 5% of outcome data are missing, a complete case analysis will be performed without imputation. If more than 5% of data are missing for any outcome, multiple imputation will be performed using chained equations to create imputed data sets in each exposure group.¹⁵ The number of data sets used will be calculated using the two-stage quadratic rule described by von Hippel.¹⁶ For any multiple imputation conducted, we will use all potential confounders and baseline variables together with study outcomes. If multiple imputation is used, all affected outcome analyses will be based on the imputed data.

All pleural culture results will supplementally be reported according to specific pathogens, resistancy, and presense of similar bacterial or fungal species in related cultures (blood and airway secretions), reported descriptively as frequencies and percentages. Additionally, we will report the numbers and frequencies of positive pleural fluid cultures from pleural fluid samples conducted ≥ 1 day after pleural drain insertion, secondarily divided in patients with a primary positive, negative or not conducted ipsilateral pleural fluid culture, to quantify pleural infections that occurred during ICU admission.

All analyses will be conducted using Stata statistical software (StataNordic).

Ethics

Permission to obtain individual patients' data from medical journals without their consent will be obtained from the Regional Council of the North Denmark Region and from the respective heads of departments as required prior to study initiation.

Processing of personal data

Data from the patients' medical journals will be collected and managed using REDCap[®] electronic data capture tools hosted at the North Denmark Region.¹⁷ Data from the microbiological databases will be stored in the encrypted hard drives of the North Denmark Region. The study will be registered as according to the Danish Data Protection Agency.

Reporting, pre-specification, and publication of results

Results will be reported as according to the Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) Statement: guidelines for reporting observational studies.¹⁸

The final protocol will be uploaded to Zenodo.org, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8064130> prior to study initiation.

Results will be published regardless of outcomes. Publication will be sought in a relevant peer reviewed journal, preferably with open access.

Conflict of interest

All research group participants report no conflicts of interests.

Funding

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